

A Study to Assess Patients Satisfaction Attending Out Patient Department at Government Tertiary Care Hospital in Junagadh District, Gujarat

Zalavadiya DD¹, Vala MC², Hala NA³, Nimavat KA⁴, Mehta DP⁵, Khandhedra SA⁶

¹Assistant Professor Department of Community Medicine GMERS Medical College Junagadh

²Assistant Professor Department of Community Medicine GMERS Medical College Junagadh

³Tutor Department of Community Medicine GMERS Medical College Junagadh

⁴Assistant Professor Department of Community Medicine GMERS Medical College Junagadh

⁵Tutor Department of Community Medicine GMERS Medical College Morbi

⁶Assistant Professor Department of Community Medicine GMERS Medical College Junagadh

Received: 25-12-2022 / Revised: 25-01-2023 / Accepted: 05-02-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Nimavat Khyati A.

Conflict of interest: Nil.

Abstract

Background: Qualitative aspect of health care delivery has been emerged to be focused as a critical area for patient management. To reform the health care system, it is very crucial to persuade the demands of Patients. Therefore, it is very necessary to assess the care to the clients/ patients in terms of satisfaction.

Methodology: A cross sectional descriptive study was conducted on patients visiting the OPD of various departments of the facility. It includes purposive sample of 150 adults between ages of 18-70 years attending OPD of various departments during the month of May in 2019. Various factors to assess the patient satisfaction were perception about the hospital admission process, pharmacy services, cleanliness, behavior of hospital staff & over all perception about the hospital.

Results: 88.7% patients were satisfied for timely registration. 95.3% patients were satisfied with the behavior of doctors. 85.3% patients were satisfied with the privacy maintained by doctor. 60% patients got their reports on time. On seeing overall patients' perception, 86% patients were satisfied with hospital services.

Conclusion: Patients' satisfaction is one of the crucial aspect to care for providing better treatment and this should be well considered by hospital management and all the staff. Patients' satisfaction regarding various service provisions was overall found satisfactory in the study.

Keywords: Patients' Satisfaction, Quality Health Care, Government.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction:

Quality of care is a global concern in today's era. It is a right of patient which is often neglected. Still today the main focus of the current health system generally reflects around quantitative aspect of service delivery, though now a days qualitative aspect of health care delivery has been emerged to be focused as a critical area for patient management.

To manage the demands of population and to be a part of the health system or health care industry, major revolutions have to be accepted. To reform the health care system, it is very crucial to persuade the demands of the clients i.e. Patients. Therefore, it is very necessary to assess the care to the clients/ patients in terms of satisfaction. [1-4] The main six aims of the quality health care system and patients' safety are (1) safe; (2) equitable; (3) evidence based; (4) timely; (5) efficient; and (6) patient centered and the last three factors directly influence patient satisfaction. [5] Majority of literature reviewed have been showing increasing satisfaction of services from patients point of views worldwide and also in India [1, 5, 6]

The review oh health system in terms of providing care and quality should be assessed very often, though one cannot find many studies on this aspect. Therefore, here this study is an effort to find the level of patients' satisfaction and factors affecting it in a tertiary care Government center of a district of Gujarat.

Objectives

- To assess the level of satisfaction among the patient attending OPD services at various areas of Hospital available at government tertiary care hospital.
- To Know the demographic characteristics of patients attending

OPDs of a Government tertiary care hospital

Materials and Methods

This cross sectional descriptive study was conducted in GMERS Civil hospital Junagadh, which is tertiary care hospital attached with a medical college. The target population was patients available in the OPD of various departments at the time of data collection who were able to listen & understand either Gujarati or English language & above 18 years. Oral consent was taken before interview of patients.

It includes purposive sample of 150 adults between ages of 18-70 years attending OPD of various departments during the month of May in 2019. Total duration of study was 3 months. Data were collected by under graduate medical students as a part of their research project. Exit interviews of Patients attending various OPDS of the hospital were taken by asking them semi structured pretested questions after taking oral consent from them to participate in the study.

The exclusion criteria for the study were patients attending emergency, pediatrics, psychiatrics department and those who have not given consent.

The variable included to assess the patient satisfaction were perception about the hospital admission process, pharmacy services, cleanliness, behavior of hospital staff & over all perception about the hospital. The answer to various services was obtained in the form of 'not satisfied' & 'satisfied'. Patients who had responded positively for more than 75% of questions were considered as satisfied with health services.

Analyses and interpretation of the data were done using appropriate software and Micro soft Excel ver. 10.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of patients attending various outpatient-based services in the hospital

Variables	No. Of patient (Percentage)
Age group	
18-25	41 (27.3%)
26-40	43 (28.7%)
41-60	56 (37.3)
60-70	10 (6.7%)
Gender	
Male	79 (52.66%)
Female	71 (47.34%)
Education	
Illiterate	24 (16%)
Primary	57 (38%)
Secondary	36 (24%)
Higher secondary	24 (16%)
Graduate	09 (6%)
Type of visit	
1 st time	63 (42%)
Follow up Visit	87 (58%)

Total numbers of respondents were 150. Table 1 shows socio demographic profile of patients attending OPDs of the hospital. About of 1/3rd of the patients i.e. 37.3% were from between age 41-60 years, followed by 28.7% were from 26-40 years age group, 27.3% were from 18-25 years of age and 6.7% were from elderly patients. Mean age of the patients attending the hospital was 38.9 years (SD-14.39 years). From the total 150 patients,

52.6% were male and 47.3% were female. Out of total patients, 38% had completed education up to primary level, while 24% and 16% patients completed their study up to secondary and higher secondary level respectively. About 16% respondents were illiterate and only 6% respondents were graduate and above. 42% patient had their 1st visit of hospital and 58% patients had come for follow up visits.

Table 2: Questions related to patients' satisfaction with various domains

Questions	Number of satisfied respondents (percentage)	Number of unsatisfied respondents (percentage)
Questions related to case Registration windows and finding correct place in hospital		
1. Waiting at registration (within 30 minutes)	133 (88.7%)	17 (11.3%)
2. Behavior of receptionist	120 (80%)	30 (20%)
3. Sufficiency of staff	82 (51.3%)	68 (48.7%)
4. Search of OPD place (proper signage and arrows available)	91 (60.7%)	59 (39.3%)
5. Lift usage	57 (38%)	93 (62%)
Questions related to OPD area and behavior of Health care staff		
1. Presence of doctor in OPD	126 (84%)	24 (16%)
2. OPD Timing	112 (74.7%)	38 (25.3%)

3. Behavior of peon	118 (78.7%)	32 (21.3%)
4. Ventilation & sitting in OPD waiting area	133 (88.7%)	17 (11.3%)
Questions related to doctor patient relationship and behavior of doctors		
1. Behavior of consultant	143 (95.3%)	07 (4.7%)
2. Consulting time	134 (89.3%)	16 (10.7%)
3. Privacy of patients	128 (85.3%)	22 (14.7%)
4. Communication of doctors with patients	145 (96.7%)	05 (3.3%)
5. Clinical Skills	144 (96%)	06 (4%)
Questions related to Investigation and Pharmacy aspects		
1. Availability of Laboratory Test	120 (80%)	30 (20%)
2. Cleanliness at laboratory	123 (82%)	27 (18%)
3. Laboratory report time	90 (60%)	60 (40%)
4. Radiology	78 (52%)	72 (48%)
5. Availability of drug from dispensary	83 (55.3%)	67 (44.7%)
6. Instructions given at drug distribution window	104 (69.3%)	46 (30.7%)
Questions related to Hospital Environment		
1. Facilities of drinking water	85 (56.7%)	65 (43.3%)
2. Facilities of toilet	48 (32%)	102 (68%)
3. Overall hospital environment satisfaction	109 (72.7%)	41 (27.3%)
Patients' overall perception		
1. Services satisfaction	129 (86%)	21 (14%)
2. Recommendation	131 (87.3%)	19 (12.7%)

Table 2 shows that when patients were asked about the services at registration window and reaching to OPDs, out of 150 patients, 88.7% patients were able for their registration on time, 80% patients were satisfied with the behavior of receptionist, 51.3% patients said that enough staff present at case window while 48.7% patients said that there is more requirement of staff at case window, 60.7% patients find OPD easily, 38% patients got lift easily while 62% patients couldn't get lift easily.

When patients were asked about the experience of services in OPD area, 84% patients answered that doctor was present when they came to OPD, 74.7% patients didn't have to wait for their appointment

for OPDs, and 78.7% patients were satisfied with the behavior of peon, 88.7% patients were satisfied with the ambiance like, ventilation and sitting arrangements of waiting area.

About asking the behavior of doctors and doctor patient relationship, out of 150 patients, 95.3% patients were satisfied with the behavior of doctors. 89.3% patients were satisfied with consultation time given by doctors to them. 85.3% patients were satisfied with the privacy maintained by doctor. 96.7% patients were satisfied with the doctor's way of communication and 96% patients felt that consultants had good clinical skill.

80% patients said that their laboratory tests were performed while 20% patients told

that their laboratory tests suggested by clinicians were not performed in the facility, 82% patients agreed that cleanliness maintained at laboratory, 60% patients got their reports on time, 52% patients told that their radiological tests were performed on time.

On asking about the services received at drug dispensary store, 55.3% patients got their all prescribed drugs from dispensary, 69.3% patients got guidance from pharmacist. 56.7% patients satisfied with facilities of drinking water, 32% patients were satisfied with toilet facilities. 72.7% patients were satisfied with the hospital environment.

On seeing overall patients' perception, 86% patients were satisfied with hospital services while 14% were not satisfied with overall services. Asking about recommendation by patients, 87.3% patients would recommend hospital to others while 12.7% won't recommend the hospital to others.

Discussion

This study was conducted in a tertiary care government hospital to assess the patients' satisfaction attending various outpatient departments of the facility. In the era of client oriented services, it is necessary to understand patients' perception and expectation to provide better services to them. This study was an effort to understand this approach in detail. Various aspects of patient related services were assessed to get the clarity of overall services given to the patients in a government hospital. Different elements like waiting time, behavior of doctors and other staff, laboratory services, cleanliness etc. were studied in detail.

For patient care, level of satisfaction is very concerned according to World Health Organization. [7] Our results showed that most of the patients (86%) were satisfied with the OPD services of the hospitals. The results were found similar with other studies. Goel S. et al. in their study

conducted in North India found that 77.3% patients were satisfied with the OPD services of health care facilities. [8]

Kumar P et al in their study in West Bengal reported that 78% of the patients were satisfied about the services. [1] Another study done in Jabalpur district of India by Sharma A et al. also found 73% participants were satisfied with availability of services like professional care, their behavior etc. [8] Other studies in different part of world also had similar findings like, Study conducted in Qatar Al Emadi and Falamarzi noted 75.2% overall satisfaction rate [9] and study conducted in Nigeria by Olusina et al. also reported 75% satisfaction rate in health care facility. [10,11]

This study showed that patients were satisfied with some important aspects like, behavior (95%) and communication by doctor (96.6%), maintenance of patient privacy (85%), ventilation (88.6%) and sitting arrangement for OPD waiting, availability of laboratory tests in hospital (80%) etc. while some factors were needed to improve like toilet facilities, reporting time of laboratories and radiology, availability of drugs, lift usage facility etc.

Conclusion

Patients' satisfaction is one of the crucial aspect to care for providing better treatment. Hospital management and all the staff working there should be cautious about this aspect. This study was an attempt to check the level of services provided in a government of facility and identify the areas needed to be strengthen for overall betterment of patients. Patients' satisfaction regarding various service provisions was overall found satisfactory in the study and good number of people would like to recommend others for the hospital which shows patients reliance for the facility.

References

1. Kumar P, Adhikari A, Ray M, Indu R, Bhattacharya S, Das AK. Assessment of patient satisfaction in outpatient department of a tertiary care hospital in West Bengal, India: a questionnaire-based study. *Int J Community Med Public Health* 2018; 5:3919-23.
2. Fisher AW. Patients Evaluation of Outpatient Medical Care. *J Med Educ.* 1971;46(3):238-44.
3. Barnett B. Women's views influence choice. *Network.* 1995;16(1):14-8.
4. Mosadeghrad AM. Factors influencing healthcare service quality. *International Journal of Health Policy and Management.* 2014;3(2):77-89.
5. Patient satisfaction surveys and quality of care: An information paper. Available at: [https://www.annemergmed.com/article/S0196-0644\(14\)00132-2/fulltext](https://www.annemergmed.com/article/S0196-0644(14)00132-2/fulltext), accessed on 31/01/2023
6. Prasanna K S, Bashith M A, Sucharitha S. Consumer satisfaction about hospital services: A study from the outpatient department of a private medical college hospital at Mangalore. *Indian J Community Med* 2009; 34: 156-9
7. Bleich SN, Ozaltin E, Murray CJ. How does satisfaction with the health-care system relate to patient experience? *Bulletin of the World Health Organization.* 2009;87(4):271-8
8. Goel, Sonu & Sharma, Deepak & Bahuguna, Pankaj & Goel, Sonika. Predictors of Patient Satisfaction in Three Tiers of Health Care Facilities of North India. 2015.
9. Al-Kuwari, Mohamed & Emadi, Nada & Falamarzi, Samya & Al-Ansari, Amna. Patients' Satisfaction with Primary Health Care Services in Qatar. *Middle East Journal of Family Medicine.* 2009, 7. 4.
10. Olusina AK, Ohaeri JU, Olatawura MO Patient and staff satisfaction with the quality of in-patient psychiatric care in a Nigerian general hospital. *Soc Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol.* 2002 Jun; 37(6): 283-8.
11. Abid Z., Ramzan M. A., Sheroze M. W., Jamal K., Batool R., & Mazher S. Prevalence of Depression and Its Association with Cigarette Smoking among Undergraduate Students; A Cross-Sectional Study from Karachi. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences.* 2022; 5(2): 1786-1790.